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Deliverable Administration and Summary

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Author(s)	Leandro Madrazo, Angel Martín Cojo (LA SALLE), Raúl Robert (SOSTRE CÍVIC), Simona Rotteglia (HERISCAPE), Lubica Fenclova (BRATISLAVA), Mihajlo Zinoski (UKIM)				
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Work Programme Description	At least three integrated participatory actions will be designed and implemented at three different locations which engage citizens, professionals, students and teachers in the definition and solution of housing problems with a local impact. The aim of the participatory actions will be to involve as many stakeholders as possible in the decision making processes to shape their living environment. Outcomes will be documented and explained in the project blogs, as well as through local media.				
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1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document contains the plans of the three participatory actions to be carried out in Barcelona, Rimini, Bratislava and Skopje during the lifetime of the project. It describes the scope of the participatory action, as well as the objectives, participants, and expected outcomes.

In Barcelona, a participatory action will be carried out by the School of Architecture La Salle and the cooperative of Sostre Cívic from October 2013 to January 2014. The purpose of the action will be to engage architecture students and future residents of this building in a collaborative process with the aim of identifying the needs of the dwellers. Therefore, this action will have a pedagogic purpose, both for the future dwellers and for the students of architecture. It will enable participants to take part in a social design process which involved citizens and designers (e.g. architecture students). Along the participatory process, students will create a set of tools to learn about the experience of the dwellers about the spaces they lived in, and to find about the spaces they would like to inhabit in the future. The final result of this collaboration will be the elaboration of a set of guidelines that the students produced after the dialogue held with the residents.

In Rimini, a participatory action will be carried out between June 2013 and April 2014, led by Heriscape and the Ordine Architetti Rimini. Ten public and private institutions participated in this action. The main purpose is to define strategies to overcome the difficulties that some segments of the population (specially, young people) have to access social housing in a medium-size city. A preliminary research of the social and legal conditions affecting social housing in the city will be carried out. Later, researchers will explain the criteria they have adopted to identify some of the social housing problems, in order to set a baseline for future actions and policies that will be implemented with the collaboration of the different organizations. As a result of the interactions in the two round tables, it is expected that the participants will learn how to consolidate and foster collaborations to provide more effective solutions to the social housing problems in Rimini. Participants will learn and implement guidelines to develop social housing proposals in collaboration with other stakeholders, thus replicating the processes followed in this participatory action.

In Bratislava, the participatory action will be implemented in 2016. This participative action in the city of Bratislava focuses on the redevelopment of the natural and recreational landscape in the Zemník area, a vestige of the Danube alluvial forests. The proximity to the district of Bratislava – Petržalka and to the nearby suburbs Jarovce and Rusovce provides an enormous recreational potential of the area. The large-scale development of the new dwelling districts Petržalka – Sunflowers and Bratislava South City, situated nearby the area, has already started. For more than thirty years, canoeists have been planning to develop this area to house sporting facilities. Before approving a proposal to build them, the city planning departments would like to hear the opinions of the stakeholder groups affected by the development: environmentalists, anglers' associations, sportsmen and general public. With this aim, a guided walk on the area has been organized for hear their opinions after explaining the purpose of the development plan.

In Skopje, a participatory action will be carried out in the academic year 2015/16 involving students and tutors from Faculty of Architecture, Ss. Cyril & Methodius University in Skopje, as well as lecturers from Polis University, Tirana, and Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade. The case study area is the municipality of Ilinden a former rural area which was rapidly urbanized during the 1960s. Despite its predominant urban character, in some fragments of the neighbourhood rural activities can still be seen. The purpose of this community action is to identify, along with the residents, potential spaces for community use. The yards located at the front of the houses, can become spaces to meet neighbours and to carry out shared activities.

2 INTRODUCTION

2.1 Purpose and target group

This is a report about participatory activities planned in the sub-network Community Participation (WP3) in Barcelona, Rimini, Bratislava and Skopje. It describes the scope of the participatory actions, as well as their objectives, participants, and expected outcomes. The target groups of the work reported in this document are all project partners, in particular members of sub-networks Housing Research (WP2) and Pedagogical Activities (WP4). Other potential readers of this document are community leaders, local administrations promoting citizen participation, professional organizations, as well as teachers and researchers involved with community action projects.

2.2 Contribution of partners

The participatory action in Barcelona is a joint initiative of the School of Architecture La Salle and Sostre Cívic. The action in Rimini involves Heriscape and the Ordine degli Architetti, Rimini, as well as number of local organizations. In Bratislava, the city of Bratislava and the Department of Architecture of the Technical University of Bratislava collaborate in the participatory action. Finally, the action in Skopje is a joint project of the University Ss. Cyril and Methodius, Macedonia; the University of Belgrade, Serbia; and Polis University, in Tirana, Albania.

2.3 Relations to other activities in the project

The work carried out in the participatory activities is expected to have an educational impact on non-academic stakeholders. In this regard, it shares some of the objectives with the activities carried out in the sub-network Pedagogical Activities (see Deliverable 4.1 “Learning Spaces”). Some of the issues addressed in these actions –such as housing regeneration, communication between professionals and non-professionals, place making and codesign, private and public collaboration and participatory planning– are also related to the work done in the sub-network Housing Research (see Deliverable 2.4 “Research matrix”).

3 BARCELONA: A PEDAGOGIC EXPERIENCE WITH CO-HOUSING

3.1 Description of the action

A participatory action will be carried out by the School of Architecture La Salle and the cooperative of Sostre Cívic from October 2013 to January 2014, in Barcelona. The purpose of this activity is to develop design methods and tools to foster the participation of dwellers in the design process of their future homes.

Sostre Cívic had been trading for over two years with the Government of Catalonia and the Barcelona City Council to set up the legal frameworks that enable new modes of accessing to housing. These models aimed to foster easy access to affordable housing, flexibility of usage, environmental savings and participation of users in the design and construction processes. The *Models de Cooperatives d'Ús* (Cooperative Models of Use) is an example of such model. Its main characteristics of this model are the following:

- The cooperative is a non-profit association
- Buildings are owned collectively by the cooperative (in this way the members do not have to pay a mortgage)
- The members of the cooperative acquire the right to use a dwelling. This right is permanent and transmissible. Therefore, the members are users, rather than owners (to avoid speculation)
- All members have the same decision power and they can decide on every aspect concerning the project, even on those regarding design and construction.

This model creates, on the members of the cooperative, a sense of ownership and belonging to their dwellings.

An on-going project promoted by Sostre Cívic to refurbish an existing multi-story building in El Born neighbourhood in Barcelona (Figure 1) provides an opportunity to bring together dwellers and architects in a participatory process aimed at defining the characteristics of the future dwellings.

Figure 1. Location of the building in the old town of Barcelona

The building to be refurbished has five stories and it was completed in the early twentieth century. Each floor-plans has around 100 square meters including the staircase, with two facades facing the street (Figure 2).

Figure 2. The case study building

3.2 Objectives

The purpose of the action will be to engage architecture students and future residents of this building in a collaborative process with the aim to identify the needs of the dwellers. Therefore, this action has a pedagogic purpose, both for the future dwellers and for the students of architecture. It will enable participants to take part in a social design¹ process involving citizens and designers (e.g. architecture students).

The expected learning outcomes for every type of learner involved in this action –students and dwellers- are the following:

- For the students of architecture:
 - To propose ways to engage dwellers in a reflective process about their present and future living place.
 - To design the tools and methods that would enable dwellers to express their knowledge and needs.
 - To learn from users –rather than from the building regulations or from established architectural models– the needs of the future dwellings.
 - To analyse the insights obtained from the interaction with dwellers and to use them as input in the design process.
- For dwellers:
 - To express and communicate their experience about the spaces they live in.
 - To assess their living environment in qualitative terms, by describing what they consider good or bad about the places they live in.
 - To provide them with a knowledge that would enable them to participate in the

¹ “Social design is working with people rather than for them; involving people in the planning and management of the spaces around them; educating them to use the environment wisely and creatively to achieve a harmonious balance between the social, physical, and natural environment”. Sommer, R. (1983). Social design: Creating buildings with people in mind. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall, Inc.

subsequent stages of the design process of their future living environment.

As a result of this interaction, it is expected that dwellers will learn to make a critical assessment of their living environment by using the communication and representation tools provided by architecture students and that students will learn to design a participatory process and to analyse and make use of the insights provided by dwellers.

3.3 Participants

Sostre Cívic is a Catalan association that promotes cooperative models to facilitate access to housing. At the present time, it has 1.257 members. Members play different roles within the association depending on their interests. The participatory activities of the seminar will be circumscribed to those members who are interested in living in the flats of the proposed building located at El Born neighbourhood.

Students from the elective seminar “Contemporary housing research” from the School of Architecture La Salle, will participate in the activities. The meetings will take place at the School of Architecture La Salle and at the premises of the Sostre Cívic cooperative, both in Barcelona.

3.4 Work plan

The activities planned for this action are grouped in the following sequential phases:

1. **Learning design:** The two partners involved on the participatory action, will prepare a working plan and a timetable (calendar, resources, etc.).
2. **Theoretical background:** Within the seminar, students will be introduced to the concepts and methods of citizen participation in architecture.
3. **Design of participatory sessions:** Architecture students will design the tools they will use to get from dweller their ideas about the way they would like to live.
4. **Implementation of the participatory sessions:** Two different sessions have been planned. For the second session, the methods and tools designed by the students will be reviewed following their implementation in the first participatory session.
5. **Eliciting knowledge:** Students will analyse the feedbacks obtained from future residents to create a brief to guide the design of the future dwellings.
6. **Dissemination:** A video will be produced to document the process and the outcomes obtained in the participatory action.

Table 1. Work plan of the participatory action in Barcelona

	Aug. 2014	Sep. 2014	Oct. 2014	Nov. 2014	Dec. 2014	Jan. 2015	Feb. 2015	Mar. 2015
1. Learning Design	Sostre Civic & pedagogic team							
2. Theoretical background			On-line and F2F lectures and classes					
3. Design of participatory sessions				Analysing, describing and evaluating participatory strategies				
4. Implementation of participatory sessions					Participatory Session 1		Participatory Session 2	
5. Eliciting knowledge							Creating a design brief	
6. Dissemination								Producing a video

3.5 Expected outcomes

The learning activities will be carried out in a dedicated learning space named [“Civic Housing”](#), created in the OIKODOMOS Workspaces environment. The students will create a set of tools to get from dwellers their experience about the spaces they lived in, and to know about the spaces they would like to inhabit in the future. The final result of this collaboration will be design guidelines that the students have produced after the dialogue held with the residents. The collaborative working process and the methods and tools applied will be documented in a video.

4 RIMINI: DEFINING STRATEGIES TO FACILITATE ACCESS TO SOCIAL HOUSING

4.1 Scope of the action

Housing demand has been transforming in Italy since the early 1990s, becoming more complex and diversified, and increased in number. It is currently characterized by the presence of “atypical” housing demand: strong increase in single households, single-parent families, immigrants, temporary workers, off-campus students and others.

Sustained by this new “atypical” demand, the extension of the housing emergency is affecting intermediate segments of the population (“grey area”) who until recently were unaffected by such difficulties. The housing needs of this part of population cannot be met on the open market due to financial reasons or to a lack of appropriate options on the supply side.

The goal of social housing is to improve the conditions of these people by favouring the creation of dignified social and living conditions so that they may not only have access to suitable dwellings, but also to rich and meaningful human relations.

Referring to policies, instruments and projects, in Italy social housing is characterized by the presence of many public and private institutions that operate at different levels addressing distinguished needs and targets. Even though they try to offer options to different people in need of social housing, the lack of coordination and cooperation often prevents these institutions from correctly identifying population demands and talking appropriate action.

The fragmentation of social housing policies, tools, projects and instruments, and the lack of collaboration between the public and private bodies dealing with social housing hinders the effectiveness of any action defined to give an answer to the housing needs of the “new” sectors (“grey area”) together with the most disadvantaged sectors of the population.

In light of the lack of public resources to sustain a social housing policy, cooperation between individuals, associations, private bodies and institutions has become necessary. In this context, the purpose of the participatory action in Rimini was to define possible and feasible strategies to support solutions for the social housing problems in a medium-size city. These strategies had to be proposed through an integrated approach involving public and private bodies participating to the action.

By defining needs and opportunities, the aim is to set some criteria for future actions and policies that have to be developed by the participants. The proposed actions will foster the collaboration among the partners in order to give effective answers to the request of social housing coming from different sectors of the population.

4.2 Objectives

The main purpose of the participatory action in Rimini is to define strategies to overcome the difficulties that some segments of the population (specially, young people) have to access social housing in a medium-size city. In this context, the participatory action proposed in Rimini has the following aims:

- To create a permanent round table with the participation of the local associations and institutions committed to facilitate access to housing and to assure the welfare of the population;
- To identify social housing problems and opportunities, to set a baseline for future actions and policies;

- To outline possible solutions and pilot actions carried out with the participation of the involved stakeholders;
- To come up with a methodological approach which contributes to establishing a broader housing policy at local and national levels;
- To establish links among OIKONET partners working on issues related to this action;
- To disseminate the outcomes of this action at the national and international level, and to evaluate their possible application to different European contexts.

4.3 Participants

The following public and private institutions are involved in this action:

- Municipality of Rimini (social housing, youth policies, urban planning)
- Carim Bank Foundation (partner of Emilia-Romagna Social Housing Fund)
- Ordine Architetti Rimini (Architect Registration Board)
- Uni.Rimini (Consortium sustaining the University of Bologna at Rimini)
- Acer Rimini (Affordable Housing Regional Agency).
- Caritas (Charity Catholic organization)
- Papa Giovanni Foundation (Catholic Associations working on poverty alleviation)
- Slash Association (Student Association)
- San Giuseppe Foundation (Non-profit organisation working with orphans and single mothers)
- Fratelli è possibile Cooperative (Organisation working on Social mediation)

4.4 Work plan

Table 2. Work plan of the participatory action in Rimini

ITEM	m1 june	m2 july	m3 august	m4 september	m5 october	m6 november	m7 december	m8 january	m9 february	m10 march
A. Collecting data on needs, opportunities, demands and supply			A.1. General Framework							
					A.2 Rimini Case study					
							A.3 Opportunities and critical aspects			
B Participation Session (OIKONET del. 3.1)	B.1. Rimini meeting								B.2 First round table	B.3 Second round table
C Definition of criteria						C.1 data processing		C.2 Proposal		C.3. Verification
D. Connections with OIKONET partners			Involvement of OIKONET partners in tasks A1-A2-A3 (critics, scientific papers..)							
E. Specific deliverables (OIKONET 3.2, 3.3)			E.1 - Written report (OIKONET deliverable 3.2)							
		E.2 Video recording			E.2 Video (del. 3.3) recording and producing					
F. Dissemination criteria						F. Social and Local media dissemination of B2 and B3			F. report and video dissemination	

To implement the participatory action in Rimini, Heriscape and Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini proposed different stages of implementation:

A. Description of Rimini context

A.1 Outlining Italian context. In the first stage, researchers (two architects from Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini) will collect data and information describing the Italian housing context.

A.2 Survey of the social housing situation in Rimini. Secondly, still in the first stage (A), the researchers will conduct a preliminary study about social housing in Rimini by analysing different information sources (among them institutional reports) and by interviews with the participants that are important local promoters in the housing sector. This first phase will enable students to assess the situation of social housing in Rimini, identifying needs, opportunities, demands and supply.

A.3 Systematization of the results obtained in the survey. At the end of the first stage, the information collected during the interviews will be analysed and systematized.

B. Round tables

The development of the participatory action will require further activities to foster the participation and collaboration of institutions, associations, and private bodies dealing with housing. With this purpose, two round tables will be organised for the second stage to discuss possible solutions to be carried out by the participants involved.

These round tables could also evolve as a permanent steering committee on Social Housing in Rimini.

The researchers (playing the role of coordinators of the round tables) will explain the criteria they have adopted to identify some of the social housing problems, in order to set a baseline for future

actions and policies that will be implemented with the collaboration of the different organizations. Each organization participating in this process should be aware of the activities carried out by other participants. Establishing a relationship between the participants will help the development of any collaboration and will strengthen the chance for the proposals to respond efficiently and effectively to the existing social housing demand.

The planned meetings will help representatives of the Rimini community to come up with common interests and strategies and to work together to develop social housing projects.

By experiencing the discussion in the round table, the participants will need to understand the importance of creating a network of institutions, associations, private bodies (etc...) to develop, thanks to their integration, effective projects to offer different options of social housing. Furthermore, a future tight collaboration could help them to apply for funds (e.g. usually private funds require big project, while the ones proposed from the third sector are too small in terms of quantity and dimension).

Rimini municipality often asks for a precise picture reflecting all the sectors represented by the institutions, organisations and associations dealing with housing in Rimini, in order to strengthen the social public policy according to the real need of the city. The round tables could help to go in this direction: the participants sharing their knowledge and experience could come up with a methodological approach, which could contribute to local housing policy.

C. Definition of criteria to define, investigate and promote actions and projects

In parallel, to develop the first and the second stage, the OIKONET partner will analyse and investigate the results coming from data collections, interviews and round tables.

A first identification of social housing problems and possible opportunities, such as proposals or projects, coming from the activities developed by the participants will be considered as a baseline for future actions and policies to be implemented by them.

D - F. Connections with OIKONET partners and dissemination

The conclusions derived from the Rimini participatory action will be disseminated among OIKONET partners by means of reports and through the OIKONET Community Participation blog <http://oikonet-communityparticipation.blogspot.com.es/>

E. OIKONET deliverables

The fifth stage is the production of the OIKONET deliverables: a written report and a video.

4.5 Expected outcomes

From the first stage of the participatory action, a definition of the general framework of Rimini case study is expected: the interviews and the collected data to help map the stakeholders' profiles. Furthermore, this information will facilitate the identification of the demands in terms of social housing of the sector of the population they are representing. The expected outcomes of the first phase are a video with the interviews to participants and a report describing the stakeholders' profiles and field of action. The stakeholders profile will be delivered to the participants as a reference tool. It will provide a description of the institution (or association), its mission, its social target, its on-going projects on-going sharing useful to share information and knowledge and also defining common actions to develop.

In the second stage, the two participatory round tables are going to be based on results obtained in the first phase, which will describe the situation of social housing in Rimini. In the first round table Heriscape and Ordine degli Architetti di Rimini will provide the tools and instruments (such as a presentation and a written synthesis of the interviews and data collection) which will help to open the debate, to enable collaboration among the participants, to make proposals and to assess the results of the interviews. Between the first round table and the second one Heriscape or Ordine will produce a report to be shared among the participants.

As a result of the interactions taking place in the two round tables, it is expected that the participants will learn how to consolidate and foster collaborations to provide more effective solutions to the social housing problems in Rimini. Participants will learn and implement guidelines to develop social housing proposals in collaboration with other stakeholders, thus replicating the processes followed in this participatory action.

A further expected outcome is the definition of a social housing proposal to be implemented by the participants, to provide the community with effective answers to their housing problems.

All this learning process will be documented in a video and in a brochure to be shared with the participants Rimini, and will be described in Deliverable 3.3 Report on participatory actions.

5 BRATISLAVA: URBAN WALK IN THE ZEMNÍK AREA

5.1 Scope of the action

This participative action in the city of Bratislava focuses on the redevelopment of the natural and recreational landscape in the Zemník area, a vestige of the Danube alluvial forests. The proximity to the district of Bratislava – Petržalka and to the nearby suburbs Jarovce and Rusovce provides an enormous recreational potential of the area. The large-scale development of the new dwelling districts Petržalka – Sunflowers and Bratislava South City, situated nearby the area, has already started (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Zemník area, Bratislava

Zemník is a 48-hectare lake on the right bank of the Danube, 2.2 km. long and 200 m. wide. According to the master plan, Zemník is a recreational area in a natural environment which should be preserved as natural ecosystem (Figure 4). It is situated in the Jarovce district, on the outskirts of the city of Bratislava. It is connected to the Danube and its intended use was as a rowing lane. Originally, it was an artificial distributary of the Danube, which arose through the mining of gravel used for the construction of the Bratislava district of Petržalka, and later for the Gabčíkovo – Nagymaros dam. The area was excavated in the decade of the 1970s between the Danube and the system of river tributaries near the Bratislava's districts of Jarovce and Rusovce. The connection with Danube was later filled in and the lake gained the character of a closed water area. It was meant to hold two Olympic sports – rowing and the canoe sprint– but it did not have the necessary infrastructure and the facilities required were never built. The ground where Zemník is situated belongs to the state and it is managed by the state organisation Vodohospodarska Vystavba. Aside from occasional training sessions, the lake remained unused for decades, and it gradually transformed into a fishing area. It is also part of the protected bird area Dunajske Luhy.

Figure 4. The south-west bank of Zemník is assigned for recreation in the natural environment and conservation of natural ecosystems (yellow colour)

Slovakia is a country that has some of the world's top canoeists, but it does not have any training centres. Athletes usually go abroad to train. Zemník is an ideal location for them due to its accessibility. For more than thirty years, canoeists have been planning to develop this area to house sporting facilities. The lake could also be used for triathlon and distance-swimming training and competitions. Zemník could also become a recreational area, a place for leisure activities for the public such as cycling, running, and skating. However, the wetlands and the risk of flooding as well as the lack of the necessary infrastructure and the presence of an access road make it difficult to use as public space. In December 2013, the Slovak association of canoe sprint signed a lease contract for the south-west bank of Zemník with Vodohospodarska Vystavba for 50 years. Once the investment plan is approved, the development will begin within three years after the leasing contract was signed.

Zemník is accessible by a concrete panel road across the Jarovce distributary that floods. It is not possible to travel on the road due to the high water level of the Danube. At present, there are steel cables with the buoys anchored into the banks, which create nine rowing lanes. The first round of the canoe sprint qualifying races took place here, and in during the summer, the Slovak championships take place.

On completion of the foreseen infrastructure, a national centre of canoeing and rowing will be built in Zemník. It will be a modern water sports centre that meets international standards. There will be a tower, a tribune and a boathouse for the canoeists and the rowers. Zemník will have the facilities to hold regular international events such as a world championship.

Water sportsmen have a sensitive approach to the anglers. That is why a 90-metre wide stretch along the north eastern shore of Zemník has remained as a fishing area for anglers, who have their seat there for years. The fishing area is frequently visited by anglers who spend days fishing in the waters. In May 2016, the preliminary year of the Petrzalka fishing marathon took place here.

The area where the national centre of canoe sprint and rowing will be built is located in the protected bird area of Dunajské Luhy. Big flocks of wintering water birds use the water surface of Zemník during the winter. Environmental protectionists proposed to keep a part of the lake of Zemník for the birds and to avoid any activity during the migration period and in the winter time. Rare bird species also belong to this place. Besides swans and wild ducks, it is possible to find grey sea eagles or black storks. According to the general city plan, the areas of the south-western bank of Zemník are considered sports training areas. A highway will be constructed across the locality of Zemník, creating a so-called by-pass highway of Bratislava. Environmental protectionists managed to negotiate that the construction of the highway bridge would pass over the narrowest part of the alluvial forest, and above Zemník. The compensation for the occupation of the land and forest will be the forestation of 20 hectares of agricultural land in the alluvial forest. This way, 20 hectares of the forest will be protected, so that birds can have their nests there. Included in the agreement is also the recovery of the water flow in the Biskupice's distributary at the opposite bank of the Danube.

5.2 Objectives

The participatory action aims are:

- to engage the general public and stakeholders in the process of the planned development in the area of Zemník
- to collect information from residents about what the activities to be held in the area
- to foster the cooperation between citizens and the involved organisations in the decision-making process of leading to specify the requirements of the future national centre of canoeing and rowing.

5.3 Participants

The following public and private institutions and the civic associations are involved in this action:

- Bratislava city (Department of urban planning):
- Slovak association of canoe sprint
- Slovak anglers' association (Bratislava V City organization)
- Slovak nature protection (regional centre in Bratislava)
- Target groups:
 - Citizens of Bratislava –general public, specialists, social groups in the locality, stakeholders, activists
 - Sportsmen, water sportsmen, anglers

5.4 Work plan

Different actions are foreseen as part of this participatory process:

- **Public informative session:** about the beginning of the participatory action: publicity and the information on the web page www.bratislava.sk, and creating of the event and invitations through the social network,
- **Urban walk:** guided walk in the area with planned stops for specialists to give explanations to participants
- **Questionnaire:** carried out on the web and at the urban walk

5.5 Expected outcomes

The results from questionnaires and the discussions in public meetings will be incorporated into

the urban study for the national centre of canoeing and rowing in the locality of Zemník.

6 SKOPJE: A COMMUNITY ACTION IN ILINDEN

6.1 Scope of the action

The participatory action will be carried out from 15 October 2015 until 17 October 2015, led by the Faculty of Architecture, Ss. Cyril & Methodius University in Skopje. The purpose of this activity will be to create a practical tool set and associated methodology to collect and analyse the perception of the dwellers in the municipality of Ilinden of their living and built environment.

Figure 5. Urban fragment from the Ilinden neighbourhood

The Municipality of Ilinden evolved from a village and became rapidly inhabited during the 1960s. It has an almost orthogonal street pattern and uniform lots (Figure 5). Despite its predominant urban character, in some fragments of the neighbourhood rural activities can still be seen.

Figure 6. Ilinden neighbourhood

Currently, there is a lack of spaces for the community (Figure 6). The purpose of this community action is to identify, along with the residents, potential spaces for community use. The semiprivate spaces, the yards located at the front of the houses, can easily become spaces to meet neighbours and to carry out shared activities (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Semiprivate zones

In order to develop a strategy to reinforce the public character of these spaces with the residents, a community action consisting of the following steps will be carried out:

STEP 1 – Informative meeting with residents where mentors and students will explain the value of the semiprivate spaces to the locals.

STEP 2 – Interactive meeting with residents to identify their needs and then map them to the spaces.

STEP 3 – Analysis and conceptualization of the resident's requirements to redefine the thresholds between private/home and public/street space.

STEP 4 – Presentation of the proposals to the local authorities of the municipality of Ilinden.

6.2 Objectives

The main goal of this participatory action is to foster the collaboration between dwellers and students of architecture in order to identify the needs of the inhabitants. Accordingly, there is a pedagogical purpose behind the action, concerning both students and dwellers who will be taking part of a social design process.

For the students of architecture:

- Students will create a tool set and associated methodology to identify the needs of dwellers based on their perception of reality.

- This experience will help students to exercise their future professional role as negotiators between dwellers and local authorities.
- Students will learn about social cohesion in the process of elaborating proposals to transform the built environment (design by research).

For dwellers:

- To learn to appreciate the qualities (physical and social) of the spaces they inhabit.
- To understand how the use of adequate building materials can enhance the existing constructions while respecting the built environment.
- To understand that the built environment is made of interrelated elements, buildings and spaces.

6.3 Participants

The participants in the action will be:

- Architecture students from the 5th year from the Faculty of Architecture in Skopje and students from the Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade will participate in the activities. The meetings will take place at the Faculty of Architecture in Skopje.
- Faculty members from the Faculty of Architecture in Skopje, Faculty of Architecture in Belgrade, and Faculty of Architecture in Polis University, Tirana.
- The inhabitants of the municipality of Ilinden

6.4 Work plan

The activities planned for this action will be implemented in the following sequential phases:

- 1. Learning design:** A working plan and timetable will be prepared by the partners involved in the participatory action.
- 2. Theoretical background:** Students will attend lectures from Dorina Papa (Faculty of Architecture, Polis University, Tirana), Mirjana Devetakovic and Tatjana Mrdjenovic (Faculty of Architecture, University of Belgrade). A workshop will be described and organized by mentors Mihajlo Zinoski and Ognen Marina and assistants Olgica Nelkovska, Stefani Solarska and Igor Medarski from the Faculty of Architecture, Skopje.
- 3. Design of participatory session:** Architecture students will create the tools and procedures to interact with the residents.
- 4. Meeting with residents:** A workshop with students and local dwellers to get their ideas and proposals about the transformation of the neighbourhood.
- 5. Eliciting knowledge:** Residents and students will collaboratively propose measures to transform the spatial structure of the neighbourhood with the assistance of mentors.
- 6. Dissemination:** A video will be produced to document the process and the outcomes obtained in the participatory action.

Table 3. Work plan of the participatory action in Skopje

	15.10.2015	16.10.2015	30.07.2016.	17.10.2015
1. Learning design	Mentors from UKIM / BELGRADE/POLIS		Mentors from UKIM/ BELGRADE/ POLIS	
2. Theoretical background	Lectures / Workshop		Lectures / Workshop	
3. Design of participatory session		Visiting the neighborhood of <u>Ilinden</u>		Visiting the neighborhood
4. Implementation of the participatory session		Implementation		Implementation
5. Eliciting knowledge		Project proposal		Implementation
6. Dissemination		Workshop video		Workshop video

6.5 Expected outcomes

As a result of this participatory action, participants will come up with a shared language which would facilitate the dialogue between experts and non-experts. This would help the local administrators to foster a dialogue with the residents with regard to the measures to be adopted in the future development of the area.

7 CONCLUSIONS

The four participatory actions encompass a variety of issues spanning from the collaborative design of domestic spaces (Barcelona), to the participation in urban renewal processes involving public and domestic spaces (Bratislava, Skopje) and the provision of social housing (Rimini). They encompass a variety of local stakeholders: residents (Barcelona, Skopje, Bratislava); representatives of local organizations and associations (Rimini, Bratislava, Skopje), municipalities (Rimini, Bratislava, Skopje); students and faculty members of architecture schools (Barcelona, Rimini, Skopje) and residents (Barcelona, Bratislava, Skopje). In all cases participation conveys different types of learning process in which experts and non-experts interact in various ways: architecture students and dwellers (Barcelona), representatives of social and economic organizations with planners (Rimini, Bratislava), urban planners and citizens (Bratislava, Skopje), and local administrators with residents (Bratislava, Skopje).